

QUADRATIC MODEL FOR MULTI-DEPOT VEHICLE ROUTING PROBLEM WITH TIME WINDOWS IN DISASTER MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: *Disasters, natural or man-made, represent a serious threat to communities and the environment, with an increasing number of affected people worldwide. Efficient disaster management, particularly in the post-disaster phase, plays a vital role in reducing the consequences of such events through the timely distribution of essential aid. Logistics is recognized as a critical component of disaster management, encompassing facility location, resource allocation, and vehicle routing. This paper addresses the Multi-Depot Vehicle Routing Problem with Time Windows (MDVRPTW), which integrates depot locations and vehicle routing, while considering the time windows that are introduced to ensure that aid reaches affected population within critical time frames. A mathematical model is proposed that improves existing mathematical formulations by incorporating realistic post-disaster constraints such as vehicle capacity, depot limitations, and time-critical service requirements. The model is validated through a case study focusing on two urban neighborhoods in Belgrade, demonstrating the effectiveness of the approach in supporting aid distribution under constrained conditions. The findings emphasize the importance of logistics operations and provide a foundation for future improvements in disaster relief planning.*

Keywords: *location-routing, disaster management, MDVRPTW*

1. INTRODUCTION

Disasters, whether they be natural or man-made, represent a serious threat to the community and the environment. In recent years, we have witnessed a significant increase in the number and expansion of disasters and their consequences. According to the research by Delforge et al. (2025), disasters in 2023 affected approximately 93.1 million people worldwide, which resulted in 86,473 fatalities, around 20,000 more than the average over the past two decades. Due to the growing trends of the negative effects of disasters, it is necessary to constantly research scientific disciplines that minimize them. Effective disaster management plays a crucial role in prevention and mitigation, offering a structured approach to preparedness, response, and recovery. Earthquakes, floods and other types of natural disasters are always accompanied by a series of consequences for the population, infrastructure, and functionality of the community. Due to disruptions in daily activities, there is often an urgent need to provide assistance to the endangered population. That assistance may include the delivery of essential supplies, evacuation or medical assistance. In such situations, it is necessary to establish a stable logistic network. Considering this, we can say that logistics is an integral component of effective disaster management.

Disaster management and logistics are recognized as an essential for properly dealing with disasters. Almost always, they are followed by uncertainty that is reflected in disruptions in transportation networks, demands for resources, severity of damage, etc. which complicates planning and decision-making. Through various studies and researches, models and methods for managing logistics activities in disasters have been developed. These activities are related to the problems of inventory management, location of facilities, vehicle routing, etc. All these activities can be classified based on the time they are carried out in relation to the occurrence of the disaster itself. Accordingly, we distinguish between pre-disaster and post-disaster phases. The pre-disaster phase includes all preparedness activities aimed at mitigating the impact of the disaster, while the post-disaster phase encompasses response and recovery efforts focused on providing assistance to the affected population. Location models can be applied in both the pre-disaster and post-disaster phases. In flood evacuation planning, location models have been used to determine optimal shelter placements (Kongsomsaksakul et al., 2005). Verma and Gaukler (2015) proposed a deterministic location model for

disaster response facilities to pre-position emergency supplies. Similarly, other authors utilize such models to address these issues in the pre-disaster phase. The majority of authors, focusing on the pre-disaster phase, deal with warehouse location and emergency supplies, as it is demonstrated by Yu (2021). While location models in pre-disaster phase are used for locating warehouses and supplies, similar models are applied in the post-disaster phase to locate temporary hospitals and distribution centers. For example, Hu et al. (2013) proposed a model combined with reliability to select the emergency distribution centers. A robust location-allocation framework for healthcare facilities was introduced by Alinaghian et al. (2021). Along with distribution centers and medical centers, location models can be used to determine the optimal locations for warehouses, shelters, and debris removal sites (Boonmee et al., 2017).

In addition to facility location models, vehicle routing models play a significant role in disaster management. These models help optimize the movement of resources, personnel and supplies to affected areas, ensuring efficient and timely delivery. Vahdani et al. (2018) address location and routing problems separately in two stages. In the first stage, facility location is established, while in the second, vehicle routing is performed. It is common for location and routing problems to be solved simultaneously so that overall optimal solution can be achieved. In that sense, mathematical model used in this research, MDVRP (eng. Multi-Depot Vehicle Routing Problem) is developed with the same goal. MDVRP model is proposed for locating local depots and distributing relief supplies by Uslu et al. (2017). Similar, Wei et al. (2020) suggested location-routing model for post-disaster relief distribution. Location-routing models can be used regardless of the type of disaster, for instance, Vieira et al. (2021) applied MDVRP to emergency water trucking. Same or relatively similar MDVRP models can be found in many publications, but there are still differences. Those differences can be reflected in the objective functions, which might aim to maximize the quality of service (Beiki et al., 2020), minimize distribution time and costs (Vahdani et al., 2018) or minimize delays (Wei et al., 2020). Other differences are reflected in concepts such as urgency of delivery or reliability of routes. Although these differences are evident and noticeable, the ultimate goal is the optimization of logistics activities in disaster management.

Logistics plays a critical role in post-disaster operations, directly impacting the ability to save lives and reduce the devastating effects of disasters. In such scenarios, time becomes one of the most crucial factors, requiring constant attention and optimization. Timely delivery of essential supplies in post-disaster operations is crucial, as delays can have severe consequences for the lives and conditions of the affected population. Any delay in delivery can have long-lasting effects and consequences. Due to the urgency of certain types of aid, there are moments and time windows in which the delivery must be completed. The aim of this paper is to highlight the importance of time windows, their introduction, and their application in post-disaster logistics operations.

The remaining of the paper is organized as follows. In the second section we presented problem description along with the MDVRPTW (eng. Multi Depot Vehicle Routing Problem with Time Windows) mathematical model, which enables optimal solving of the described problem. In the third section, the MDVRPTW is applied to a case study to demonstrate the functionality of the model. Finally, the conclusion remarks are given in the last section, along with suggestions for further research to enhance the effectiveness of post-disaster logistics operations.

2. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION AND MODEL FORMULATION

After a disaster, due to the probable infrastructure damage, it is necessary to establish an adequate logistics network for aid distribution which includes a set of distribution facilities on an affected region. In conditions after a disaster every user j from the set $J = \{1, 2, \dots, |J|\}$ who requires relief, has a specific time window $[T1_j, T2_j]$ during which user must receive an assistance. Time windows are defined by the moment when the need for aid arises ($T1$) and the latest moment a user can wait without an assistance ($T2$). It is crucial to respect time windows because it reduces consequences of the disaster. Accordingly, it is necessary to use a certain number of local depots from the set $I = \{|J|+1, |J|+2, \dots, |J|+I\}$ which represents a set of potential locations of local depots. Besides the relief goods, the available fleet of distribution vehicles is another key resource. To efficiently distribute and satisfy user requirements it is necessary to define the routes of available delivery vehicles from the set $V = \{1, 2, \dots, |V|\}$ with limited capacity q through the network of nodes $N = \{1, 2, \dots, n, \dots, |J|, |J|+1, |J|+2, \dots, |J|+I\}$. The problem was addressed using the MDVRPTW model, which was developed as follows. Based on the constraints introduced in the works (Wei et al., 2020) and (Xu et al., 2023), the model outlined in study (Golubović et al., 2024) has been further improved in this research. In this way, new constraints were added to the already existing model, which more closely describe the problems that can be encountered in real situations. Proposed model is used for locating local depots and routing delivery vehicles while respecting time constraints imposed by the users.

The notation used in this model is presented below:

Sets

$J = \{1, 2, \dots, |J|\}$ – a set of nodes on a network representing users requesting service

$I = \{|J|+1, |J|+2, \dots, |J|+I\}$ – a set of nodes on a network representing potential locations of local depots

$N = J \cup I = \{1, 2, \dots, n, \dots, |J|, |J|+1, |J|+2, \dots, m, \dots, |J|+I\}$ – a set of all nodes on a network

$V = \{1, 2, \dots, |V|\}$ – set of distribution vehicles

$K = \{1, 2, \dots, |K|\}$ – a set of tours

Parameters

fc – costs of opening a local depot

Q – local depot capacity

q – vehicle capacity

p – the cost of unsatisfied customer requirements per unit of goods

d_j – demand of user j

st – service time

t_{nm} – the delivery time from node n to node m

$T1_j$ – the moment when the need for help by user j arises (left hand side of a time window for user j)

$T2_j$ – the latest moment for the delivery of relief goods at user j (right hand side of a time window for user j)

j)

Variables

δ_i – 1 if local depot i is opened; 0 otherwise

φ_{ik} – 1 if tour k is assigned to local depot i ; 0 otherwise

x_{nmk} – 1 if node m is visited immediately after node n within tour k ; 0 otherwise

y_{jk} – 1 if user j is served in tour k ; 0 otherwise

u_v – 1 if vehicle v is used; 0 otherwise

l_{kv} – 1 if vehicle v is assigned to tour k ; 0 otherwise

λ_{iv} – 1 if vehicle v is assigned to local depot i ; 0 otherwise

T_n – moment of arrival at node n

μ_j – quantity of goods sent to user j

γ – the amount of unsatisfied demands

The mathematical formulation of the proposed model is presented below:

$$\min z = \sum_{n \in N} \sum_{m \in N} \sum_{k \in K} t_{nm} x_{nmk} + p\gamma + fc \sum_{i \in I} \delta_i \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{i \in I} \varphi_{ik} \leq 1 \quad (\forall k \in K) \quad (2)$$

$$\varphi_{ik} \leq \delta_i \quad (\forall k \in K, i \in I) \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{j \in J} x_{ijk} = \varphi_{ik} \quad (\forall k \in K, i \in I) \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{j \in J} x_{jik} = \varphi_{ik} \quad (\forall k \in K, i \in I) \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{m \in N} x_{nmk} = \sum_{m \in N} x_{mnk} \quad (\forall n \in N, k \in K) \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{i \in I} \sum_{j \in J} x_{jik} \leq 1 \quad (\forall k \in K) \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_{i \in I} \sum_{e \in I} \sum_{k \in K} x_{iek} = 0 \quad (8)$$

$$\sum_{n \in N} x_{njc} = y_{jc} \quad (\forall k \in K, j \in J) \quad (9)$$

$$\sum_{k \in K} y_{jk} \leq 1 \quad (\forall j \in J) \quad (10)$$

$$\sum_{v \in V} l_{kv} \leq 1 \quad (\forall k \in K) \quad (11)$$

$$\sum_{v \in V} l_{kv} \geq y_{jk} \quad (\forall k \in K, j \in J) \quad (12)$$

$$\sum_{k \in K} l_{kv} \leq |K|u_v \quad (\forall v \in V) \quad (13)$$

$$\sum_{k \in K} l_{kv} \geq u_v \quad (\forall v \in V) \quad (14)$$

$$\mu_j = d_j \sum_{k \in K} y_{jk} \quad (\forall j \in J) \quad (15)$$

$$d_j \sum_{n \in N} \sum_{k \in K} x_{njk} \geq \mu_j \quad (\forall j \in J) \quad (16)$$

$$\sum_{j \in J} d_j - \sum_{h \in J} \mu_h = \gamma \quad (17)$$

$$\varphi_{ik} y_{jk} = Z_{ijk} \quad (\forall k \in K, j \in J, i \in I) \quad (18)$$

$$\sum_{j \in J} \mu_j \sum_{k \in K} Z_{ijk} \leq Q \quad (\forall i \in I) \quad (19)$$

$$\sum_{j \in J} y_{jk} \mu_j \leq q \quad (\forall k \in K) \quad (20)$$

$$\sum_{k \in K} \varphi_{ik} l_{kv} \leq |K| \lambda_{iv} \quad (\forall i \in I, v \in V) \quad (21)$$

$$\sum_{i \in I} \lambda_{iv} \leq 1 \quad (\forall v \in V) \quad (22)$$

$$T1_j \leq T_j \leq T2_j \quad (\forall j \in J) \quad (23)$$

$$T_m \geq T_n + (st + t_{nm} * x_{nmk}) - M(1 - x_{nmk}) \quad (\forall n, m \in J) \quad (24)$$

$$T_m \geq T_n + (t_{nm} * x_{nmk}) - M(1 - x_{nmk}) \quad (\forall n \in I, m \in J) \quad (25)$$

$$\delta_i, \varphi_{ik}, x_{nmk}, y_{jk}, u_v, l_{kv}, \lambda_{iv} \in \{0,1\} \quad (\forall k \in K, j \in J, i \in I, n, m \in N) \quad (26)$$

$$\mu_j, \gamma, \beta_{nk} \geq 0 \quad (\forall n \in I, j \in J, k \in K) \quad (27)$$

The objective function (1) aims to minimize costs associated with opening depots, unsatisfied requests and transportation through the network. Each tour k can only be assigned to one depot (2), and any depot that is assigned to a tour must be located (3). Constraint sets (4), (5) and (6) ensure that each tour begins and ends at its corresponding depot and that every vehicle must leave the node it enters. Additionally, each vehicle can only return to a located depot once within a single tour (7). Constraint (8) prevents direct movement between two local depots. Constraint sets (9) and (10) guarantee that each user within a tour is served exactly once. Each tour must be completed by only one vehicle, as it is defined by restriction (11). Every tour must be assigned to a service vehicle (12), with the possibility that each vehicle can do multiple tours (13) and (14). Sets of constraints (15), (16), and (17) describe the quantities delivered to users, as well as any unsatisfied requests. Constraint sets (18) and (19) ensure that local depots do not exceed their capacity, while vehicle capacity is limited by constraints (20). Expression (21) ensures that a vehicle can only be assigned to a tour if the tour and the vehicle are assigned to the same depot. Additionally, each vehicle can be assigned to only one depot (22). Constraint sets (23), (24), and (25) define the time windows within which users must be served. The nature of variables is provided by expressions (26) and (27).

3. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

To demonstrate the practical application of the proposed MDVRPTW model, this numerical example utilizes an illustrative example that reflects real challenges in aid distribution after the disaster. Two municipalities in the city of Belgrade were observed: Karaburma and Mirijevo. These areas municipalities are home to a population of 150000 residents. Due to their characteristics, these neighborhoods were considered as a part of the central urban area, which is reflected in heavy traffic congestion and slower vehicle movement. Accordingly, the delivery vehicle speed in this example was set at 30 km/h. For users, i.e. points where aid needs to be delivered, 20 locations were randomly selected. In addition to the users and demand, potential locations for local depots also had to be selected and state institutions such as health care centers were considered for several reasons. First, these facilities already provide the necessary infrastructure, reducing the costs and time required for adaptation or potential expansion. Additionally, these facilities are typically strategically located, ensuring good connectivity with other key points in the region. Furthermore, by using existing facilities, the need to build new facilities is eliminated, which reduces the time of implementation of all planned activities. Accordingly, in the considered area, 5 potential locations for local depots were identified (Figure 1).

As previously mentioned, each user has a specific time window within which this need must be fulfilled. These time constraints, along with the corresponding demand quantities, were considered in the model formulation. In accordance with the example, the vehicle capacity was set to 100 units. Implementation of the given model requires the distances between relevant locations. In this case, the key points include existing healthcare facilities selected as potential locations and the users requiring services. All users are numbered from 1 to 20, while the potential depot locations are numbered from 21 to 25. Time windows and demands of every user are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Users demands and time windows

j	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
$T1j$	2.4	0.5	2	2.3	2.1	0	2.5	1.3	1.4	2.5	2.7	0.5	1	2.5	0.4	2	2.3	1.1	0.2	1.2
$T2j$	2.5	0.6	2.1	2.4	2.2	0.1	2.6	1.4	1.5	2.6	2.8	0.6	1.1	2.6	0.5	2.1	2.4	1.2	0.3	1.3
d_j	25	18	37	31	30	23	34	14	43	23	49	12	24	40	24	43	38	34	46	15

The presented model found the optimal solution for the observed problem. The demands of all 20 users were fully satisfied through the deployment of 5 vehicles operating across 9 routes, with the strategic location of 2 local depots. This configuration ensured an efficient allocation of resources and effective coverage of all service areas. The graphical presentation of the locations and vehicle routes is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Users, local-depots and routes of vehicles

4. CONCLUSION

-This paper highlights the crucial role of optimized logistics in effective disaster response and recovery efforts, which include various operations such as aid distribution, evacuation, and health care. Optimization in logistics not only influence resources reduction, but also significantly mitigates the consequences of disasters. This study specifically focuses on the implementation of MDVRPTW model as a mean of optimizing logistics operations. The proposed model is a modification of existing ones, tailored as a practical solution for locating local depots and distributing relief. It considers the dynamic nature of relief requests, which arise at different times, emphasizing the importance of delivering aid within specific, urgent time windows. This adaptability enables more reliable planning under the unpredictable conditions typical of disaster zones, ensuring faster deployment and more effective resource utilization. Ultimately, this improves response capabilities and supports faster recovery in affected regions. Beyond disaster management, the principles of this model could be extended to other time-sensitive logistics applications, such as medical supply distribution or emergency

response in urban areas. Future research could explore integrating real-time data feeds, such as weather updates or road conditions, or leveraging artificial intelligence and machine learning for adaptive route optimization. Additionally, practical challenges in real-world implementation, such as infrastructure limitations or coordination between multiple agencies, should be further investigated.

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